

Brand Guidelines

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Brand Strategy

An aerial photograph of a rolling agricultural landscape. The left side shows vibrant green fields, while the right side shows golden-brown fields, likely wheat or corn, with distinct furrows and rows. The fields are separated by a white circular graphic element that frames the text.

Vision

The vision of the EU4Advice project is to transform short food supply chains (SFSC) into sustainable, collaborative and resilient tools that benefit producers, consumers and ecosystems through a connected network of advisors and key actors across Europe.

Mission

The mission of EU4Advice is to:

- Create and consolidate a European network of SFSC advisors.
- To empower advisors as catalysts for knowledge transfer from research to practice.
- Promote the integration of SFSC advisors in the Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKIS).
- Encourage the co-construction of innovative solutions through Living Labs in different European countries.

Target Audience

Primary

- SFSC advisors (public and private).
- Producers and actors in short food chains.
- Researchers in agri-food systems.
- Policy makers at local, regional, national and European level.

Secondary

- Consumers interested in sustainable food chains.
- Non-governmental organisations (NGOs) involved in sustainability and agriculture.
- European food chain co-operation projects.

Personality

Archetypes

Brand archetypes are powerful tools used to define a brand's personality and create a distinctive identity. Derived from universal stories, values, and characters, these archetypes resonate with our collective consciousness.

By aligning our brand with an archetype, we can connect emotionally with our audience and stand out in a remarkable way, by utilizing a tone of voice that is appropriate for the recipients of our messages.

The Sage

Focus on knowledge: EU4Advice acts as a catalyst for learning, disseminating data, analysis and evidence-based practices to guide advisors and key stakeholders in making informed decisions.

Rigour and reflection: Addresses complex food chain challenges with in-depth analysis and practical solutions that transform research into action.

Global vision: Helps to understand the complexities of the European food system and provides tools to solve local challenges with wider impact.

The Caregiver

Commitment to communities: Promotes the well-being of producers, consumers and advisors by building support networks and providing solutions that protect both people and the environment.

Empathetic collaboration: Listens and responds to the needs of all stakeholders, ensuring an inclusive and equitable approach.

Sustainability as a pillar: Works to protect natural resources and promote responsible practices that benefit future generations.

Visual Tools

Logo

Color

Introduction to the selected color palette for a brand

The brand's color scheme includes the primary, secondary, accent (or exception to use in case of an error), and neutral colors such as white or grey.

The primary color is the most dominant and recognizable color of the brand, followed by the secondary colors that complement and contrast with the primary color.

The secondary colors are ordered according to the priority indicated in the diagram on the right, where the top color has higher priority than the bottom color.

Refer to the diagram on the right for specific colors.

Sea Green ^{Primary}

#2D8461
R45 G132 B97
C66 M0 Y27 K48

Beaver ^{Primary}

#A48878
R164 G136 B120
C0 M17 Y27 K36

White ^{Neutral}

#FFFFFF
R255 G255 B255
C0 M0 Y0 K0

Karry ^{Secondary}

#FFDBC2
R255 G219 B194
C0 M14 Y24 K0

Black ^{Neutral}

#000000
R0 G0 B0
C60 M40 Y40 K100

Mint Green ^{Secondary}

#A0D8AC
R160 G216 B172
C26 M0 Y20 K15

Dark Puce ^{Texts}

#494441
R73 G68 B65
C0 M7 Y11 K71

Brunswick Green ^{Accent}

#1D5941
R29 G89 B65
C67 M0 Y27 K65

Color

Gradient table

Specification of the gradient table

The gradient table indicates which neutral color (black or white) to use for writing text based on the percentage of opacity.

Refer to the adjacent table for more information.

100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
-------------	-------------	-------------	-------------	-------------

80%	80%	80%	80%	80%
60%	60%	60%	60%	60%
40%	40%	40%	40%	40%
20%	20%	20%	20%	20%

Typography

Title

The font displayed is intended for use only in titles and subtitles.

Aa

Titles

[Download here](#)

Golos Text Bold

Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff Gg Hh Ii Jj
Kk Ll Mm Nn Oo Pp Qq Rr Ss
Tt Uu Vv Ww Xx Yy Zz

0123456789

[(@#%\$^&)]”<>!?

Typography

Aa Bb

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Paragraph

The font displayed on the page is intended for use in paragraphs only.

[Download here](#)

Golos Text Regular

Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff Gg Hh Ii Jj
Kk Ll Mm Nn Oo Pp Qq Rr Ss
Tt Uu Vv Ww Xx Yy Zz

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[(@#%\$^&)]”<>!?

Mockups

Title Example

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Title Example

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Title Example

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Ut wisi enim ad minim veniam, quis nostrud exercitation ullamcorper suscipit lobortis nisl ut aliquip ex ea commodo consequat. Duis autem vel eum iriure dolor in hendrerit in vulputate velit esse molestie consequat, vel illum dolore eu feugiat nulla facilisis at vero eros et accumsan et iusto odio dignissim.

The Network of Advisors in Short Food Supply Chains across Europe

Multi-actor collaboration dynamics and capacity building network inside and between AKIS to foster the upscaling of SFSCs across Europe

What do we want to get?

Identify and characterize SFSC advisors across Europe

Connect SFSC advisors from the 27 MSs in a European network

Improve the understanding of the main issues and challenges of European AKIS

Integrate SFSC advisors and contents into national AKIS

Interact with relevant national, regional & local policy-makers

Replicate and disseminate innovations on SFSC

How are we going to make it?

Living Labs:
4 labs testing innovative governance models with advisors, researchers, policymakers, farmers, and consumers.

Capacity Building:
Facilitating knowledge transfer to empower SFSC actors.

Advisor Integration:
Boosting advisors' roles in translating research into practice and integrating them into national Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKIS).

What to expect?

Short food supply chains (SFSC) are a mean for both producers and consumers to gain better positions in the value chain, improving trust, transparency, food quality and safety. The EU-funded EU4Advice project aims to bolster SFSC-related advisory services to chain actors, to help them make their practices more economically, socially and environmentally sustainable, connecting SFSC-advisors from the 27 member States in a common network, integrating SFSC-related advisory services, tools and contents into national Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKIS), and improving AKIS governance.

A network of 4 Living Labs to test innovative governance models, involving advisors, researchers, policy-makers, farmers and consumers

Boost the role of advisors as catalysers of the knowledge flow from research to practice

Effective capacity building of SFSC actors through fluent knowledge transfer

Effective integration of SFSC advisors into national AKIS

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Project partners

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